

THE FORMULATION OF A COMPETITIVE STRATEGY FOR A GROUP CAN USE THE BCG AND SWOT MATRICES

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Abstract

The food and beverage industry is highly competitive due to the increasing number of business players and changing consumer preferences. This situation requires companies to formulate competitive strategies that are not only oriented toward short-term sales achievements but also focused on long-term business sustainability. This study aims to analyze the current competitive strategy of Bisa Group and to formulate an appropriate long-term competitive strategy using SWOT analysis and the Boston Consulting Group (BCG) Matrix. This research employs a descriptive qualitative approach, using primary data obtained through observation and interviews, and secondary data collected from company documents and relevant literature. SWOT analysis is conducted by developing the Internal Factor Evaluation (IFE) and External Factor Evaluation (EFE) matrices, determining the company's position in the SWOT quadrant diagram, and formulating strategies based on the SWOT matrix. Furthermore, the BCG Matrix is applied to identify the position of the restaurant brand portfolio based on market growth rate and relative market share. The results indicate that Bisa Group is positioned in Quadrant I of the SWOT diagram, with an IFE score difference of 1.75 and an EFE score difference of 1.62, showing that the company is in a favorable condition and can implement an aggressive growth strategy (SO strategy). The BCG Matrix analysis shows that Sushi Tei and Pepper Lunch are categorized as Stars, while Paradise Dynasty and Marutama Ramen are categorized as Question Marks. The recommended strategy for Stars is to maintain and strengthen market position, whereas Question Marks require growth strategies through market penetration, market development, and product innovation. The proposed action plan is expected to serve as a guideline for Bisa Group in formulating and implementing long-term competitive strategies to improve competitiveness and sales performance.

Keywords: *Competitive Strategy, SWOT, BCG Matrix, Bisa Group, Food and Beverage Industry*

INTRODUCTION

The food and beverage industry is a business sector that has a high level of competition along with the increasing number of business actors and changes in consumer preferences. These competitive conditions require companies to be able to formulate competitive strategies that not only focus on achieving short-term sales but are also oriented toward long-term business sustainability. In facing these conditions, companies need to understand their business position comprehensively in order to determine the appropriate strategic direction. BG Company is a company engaged in the food and beverage industry that was established in 2004 in Medan City and manages various restaurant brands that are widely recognized by the public, including Sushi Tei, Pepperlunch, Paradise Dynasty, and Marutama Ramen. As a company that manages several brands with different characteristics and market segments, BG Company faces increasingly complex competitive dynamics, both in terms of competitors, changes in consumption trends, and technological developments. The marketing strategy that has been implemented by BG Company has mainly focused on digital-based marketing through social media such as Instagram, WhatsApp, and Facebook. The implementation of this strategy aims to reach consumers more broadly and adapt to technological developments and changes in consumer behavior. However, in its implementation, this strategy has not been able to provide optimal results, as indicated by a decline in sales. This decline in sales indicates that the strategy implemented has not been fully effective in increasing the company's competitiveness amid increasingly intense competition. Based on these problems, it is necessary to formulate a more systematic and integrated long-term competitive strategy by combining SWOT analysis and the BCG Matrix. This approach is expected to provide a clearer overview of the company's position and serve as a basis for strategic decision-

making in order to improve competitiveness and sales performance. Therefore, this research is presented in a thesis entitled “Formulating Long-Term Competitive Strategies Using the BCG Matrix and SWOT Analysis at BG Company.”

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Competitive Strategy

According to research by Hossain and Kader (2020), competitive strategy is an approach used by companies to maintain their market position and enhance competitive advantage through the utilization of the company’s internal resources and capabilities. Competitive strategy is also influenced by the dynamics of competition and changes in consumer needs. Meanwhile, Ismail, Rose, and Uli (2021) state that competitive strategy plays an important role in helping companies adapt to a competitive business environment and support the achievement of long-term performance through systematic and sustainable planning. Based on the theories above, competitive strategy can be defined as an approach and planning process used by companies to maintain market position, enhance competitive advantage, and adapt to competitive dynamics and changes in consumer needs in order to achieve sustainable long-term performance.

2. SWOT Analysis

According to Gürel and Tat (2020), SWOT analysis is used to identify the internal and external conditions of an organization by categorizing strategic factors into strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. This analysis helps companies understand their business position comprehensively. Research by Phadermrod, Crowder, and Wills (2020) states that SWOT analysis is an effective tool in the strategy formulation process because it is able to integrate internal and external factors as a basis for strategic decision-making. Based on the theories above, SWOT analysis can be defined as a strategic analysis tool used to identify and evaluate a company’s strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats as a basis for formulating and making competitive strategy decisions.

3. Boston Consulting Group (BCG) Matrix

According to Azeem and Kumar (2021), the Boston Consulting Group (BCG) Matrix is used to analyze a company’s product portfolio based on market growth rate and relative market share. This matrix helps companies determine product development priorities and resource allocation. In addition, Rothaermel (2021) states that the BCG Matrix can be used as a strategic decision-making tool to identify the position of products within the market life cycle and determine the appropriate strategic direction for each product. Based on the theories above, the Boston Consulting Group (BCG) Matrix can be defined as a portfolio analysis tool used to determine the position of a company’s products based on market growth rate and relative market share in order to determine development priorities and resource allocation.

4. Formulating Long-Term Competitive Strategies Using SWOT and the BCG Matrix

According to Oreski (2020), combining several strategic analysis tools can provide more comprehensive results in formulating a company’s long-term strategy. SWOT analysis is used to identify internal and external conditions, while the BCG Matrix is used to determine the position of products in the market. Research by Setiawan and Nugroho (2022) states that the integrated use of SWOT analysis and the BCG Matrix can help companies formulate more focused long-term competitive strategies, particularly in determining product development priorities and marketing strategies. Based on the theories above, the formulation of long-term competitive strategies using SWOT analysis and the BCG Matrix can be defined as a strategic formulation process that considers internal and external conditions as well as the company’s product position in order to enhance competitiveness and business sustainability.

METHOD

This study uses a descriptive research design with a qualitative approach. The descriptive method is applied to systematically describe the competitive strategy implemented by BG Company, particularly in terms of marketing activities, product positioning, and the company’s competitiveness within the food and beverage industry. This research does not manipulate variables but describes the company’s condition as it exists during the study. The qualitative approach is supported by quantitative calculations through the Internal Factor Evaluation (IFE) Matrix, External Factor Evaluation (EFE) Matrix, and the Boston Consulting Group (BCG) Matrix analysis. These calculations are used to increase the objectivity of the analysis in evaluating the company’s internal and

external conditions and determining the product portfolio position based on market growth rate (MGR) and relative market share (RMS). In this study, PT Adi Perkasa is used as a comparison company to analyze the relative strategic position, particularly in calculating relative market share within the BCG Matrix. However, the formulation and recommendation of competitive strategies focus entirely on BG Company as the main research object. Data sources consist of primary and secondary data. Primary data were obtained through direct observation of company activities and interviews with management and related parties. Secondary data were collected from company documents, sales reports, and relevant books and journals. Data analysis methods include SWOT analysis and the BCG Matrix. SWOT analysis is used to identify internal and external factors consisting of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats through the preparation of the IFE and EFE matrices and the determination of the company's strategic position. Meanwhile, the BCG Matrix is used to determine the company's product portfolio position based on market growth rate and relative market share. The results of these analyses are then used to formulate long-term competitive strategies to improve competitiveness and business sustainability.

Research Location and Time

This research was conducted at BG Company in Medan City. The location was chosen because the company operates in the food and beverage industry and faces relevant issues related to declining sales performance and the need for long-term competitive strategies. The research was conducted from October 2024 to January 2026, covering data collection, data analysis using SWOT and BCG Matrix methods, and the preparation of research results.

Research Object

The object of this research is the long-term competitive strategy of BG Company, which operates in the food and beverage industry. The study focuses on the company's strategies in facing market competition, particularly in marketing activities, product positioning, and efforts to improve competitiveness. The analysis examines the company's internal and external conditions, implemented marketing strategies, and the position of its product portfolio using SWOT analysis and the BCG Matrix.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework explains the relationship between internal and external company conditions and the business portfolio position in formulating long-term competitive strategies at BG Company. Internal factors are analyzed using the IFE Matrix, while external factors are analyzed using the EFE Matrix. The results are then processed through SWOT analysis to identify the company's strategic position. In addition, market growth rate and relative market share are analyzed using the BCG Matrix to determine the position of each business unit in the company's portfolio. The integration of SWOT and BCG analysis results serves as the basis for formulating long-term competitive strategies to improve competitiveness and sales performance.

Research Flowchart

The research flowchart illustrates the systematic stages of the study. The research begins with identifying the problems faced by the company, particularly increasing competition in the food and beverage industry and declining sales performance. The next stage is data collection, followed by SWOT analysis to identify internal and external factors. After that, the BCG Matrix analysis is conducted to determine the product portfolio position. The results of these analyses are then used to formulate long-term competitive strategies, which form the basis for drawing conclusions and preparing research recommendations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SWOT Analysis

SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) is used to identify and evaluate internal and external factors that influence a company's competitive strategy. Internal factors consist of strengths and weaknesses, while external factors consist of opportunities and threats originating from the business environment. In this study, SWOT analysis is conducted using the Internal Factor Evaluation (IFE) Matrix and External Factor Evaluation (EFE) Matrix.

Internal Factor Evaluation (IFE) Matrix of BG Company

The IFE Matrix is used to analyze the internal factors of BG Company consisting of strengths and weaknesses. Each factor is assigned a weight and rating based on its influence on company performance. Based on the IFE Matrix calculation, BG Company obtained a total internal score of 2.65, indicating that the company’s internal condition is relatively strong. The main strengths include high product quality (0.80) and strong brand recognition (0.72). In addition, service and operational standards as well as employee skills also contribute positively to company performance. Overall, the IFE results show that BG Company possesses strong internal capabilities to compete in the food and beverage industry.

Table Internal Factor Evaluation (IFE) Matrix of BG Company

Internal Factors	Weight	Rating	Score
Strengths			
Quality of food and beverage products	0.20	4	0.80
Well-known restaurant brands	0.18	4	0.72
Service and operational standards	0.17	4	0.68
Employee skills	0.15	3	0.45
Total Strengths	0.70		2.65

Based on the results of the IFE Matrix calculation for BG Company, the total internal factor score is 2.65, indicating that the company’s internal condition is relatively strong and supportive. The company’s main strengths come from the quality of food and beverage products, with a score of 0.80, and well-known restaurant brands, with a score of 0.72. In addition, service and operational standards as well as employee skills also contribute positively to the company’s performance.

External Factor Evaluation Matrix of BG Company

The EFE Matrix is used to analyze external factors affecting BG Company, which include opportunities and threats. The results of the EFE Matrix calculation for BG Company are presented in Table 3.3.

Table EFE Matrix of BG Company

External Factors	Weight	Rating	Score
Opportunities			
Growth in food and beverage consumption	0.25	4	1.00
Development of food delivery services	0.22	4	0.88
Consumer loyalty to the brand	0.18	4	0.72
Total Opportunities	0.65		2.60
Threats			
Intense industry competition	0.18	3	0.54
Increase in operational costs	0.10	3	0.30
Changes in consumer preferences	0.07	2	0.14
Total Threats	0.35		0.98
Total EFE Score	1.00		3.58

Based on the results of the EFE Matrix calculation for BG Company, the total score obtained is 3.58, indicating that the company has a good ability to take advantage of opportunities and face threats from the external environment. The largest opportunities come from the growth in food and beverage consumption and the development of food delivery services, while the main threat comes from the high level of industry competition. Overall, the results of the EFE Matrix show that the external opportunities of BG Company are more dominant than the threats, placing the company in a favorable external position

THE FORMULATION OF A COMPETITIVE STRATEGY FOR A GROUP CAN USE THE BCG AND SWOT MATRICES

Gilbert Citra et al

Figure SWOT Diagram of BG Company

In BG Company, the difference between strengths and weaknesses in the IFE Matrix is 1.75, while the difference between opportunities and threats in the EFE Matrix is 1.62. These values place BG Company in Quadrant I of the SWOT diagram, indicating that the company is in a favorable condition because it possesses dominant internal strengths and external opportunities. Therefore, the appropriate strategy to implement is the SO (Strength–Opportunity) strategy, which focuses on aggressive growth. As a comparison, PT Tritunggal Adi Perkasa is also positioned in Quadrant I, with an IFE difference of 1.90 and an EFE difference of 1.47. This indicates that both companies are in a growth position. However, in this research, PT Tritunggal Adi Perkasa is only used as a comparison of strategic position, while the main focus of analysis and long-term strategy formulation remains on BG Company.

	Strengths	Weaknesses
SW and OT Factors	1. High quality of food and beverage products 2. Well-known restaurant brands 3. Good service and operational standards 4. Skilled employees in service	1. Product prices are relatively high 2. Limited menu innovation 3. Digital marketing is not yet optimal

Table 3.4 SWOT Analysis of BG Company

	ST Strategy	WT Strategy
Threats	1. Maintain product quality and service standards to face increasing industry competition. 2. Utilize brand strength to maintain market position amid competition.	1. Improve the effectiveness of digital marketing to deal with competitive pressure. 2. Conduct periodic menu evaluations to adjust to changes in consumer preferences.

Source: Processed data (2025)

The SO strategy that can be implemented by BG Company is to maintain and improve the quality of food and beverage products, utilize strong restaurant brand recognition to expand the market through delivery services, and improve service quality to maximize growth opportunities in the food and beverage industry. This strategy is consistent with the company’s position in Quadrant I of the SWOT diagram, which indicates a growth-oriented strategy. Based on the results of the IFE and EFE Matrix analysis, BG Company has an IFE score difference of 1.75 and an EFE score difference of 1.62, indicating that internal strengths and external opportunities are more dominant than weaknesses and threats. As a comparison, PT Tritunggal Adi Perkasa is also positioned in Quadrant I with an IFE score difference of 1.90 and an EFE score difference of 1.47. This indicates that both companies are in a growth condition. However, in this research, PT Tritunggal Adi Perkasa is only used as a comparison of strategic position, while the main focus of analysis and strategy formulation remains on BG Company.

BCG Analysis

The BCG analysis includes the calculation of market growth rate and relative market share. The results of these calculations are used to determine the business position according to the Boston Consulting Group (BCG) Matrix as well as the strategies that can be implemented based on the position of each business unit. BCG analysis includes the calculation of market growth rate and relative market share. The results of these calculations are used to determine the business position according to the Boston Consulting Group (BCG) Matrix as well as the strategies that can be implemented based on the position of each business unit.

Market Growth Rate (MGR) of BG Company

Market growth rate (MGR) is calculated to determine the percentage increase in the company's sales from the previous year to the current year. The calculation is carried out using the following formula:

$$TPP = \frac{VP_n - VP_{n-1}}{VP_{n-1}} \times 100\%$$

$$TPP = \frac{185.000.000 - 120.000.000}{120.000.000} \times 100\%$$

$$TPP = 54.17\%$$

Based on the calculation results, the market growth rate of BG Company is 54.17%. This value indicates that there has been a significant increase in sales compared to the previous year. Theoretically, in the BCG Matrix, a market growth rate above the industry average is categorized as a high growth market. The value of 54.17% indicates that the company operates in a rapidly growing market. This condition reflects an increase in consumer demand as well as the effectiveness of the marketing and operational strategies implemented. However, markets with high growth are generally accompanied by increasingly intense competition, so the company needs to maintain consistent performance in order to remain competitive.

Relative Market Share (RMS) of BG Company

Relative market share (RMS) is calculated to determine the company's position compared to its main competitor. The calculation is carried out using the following formula:

$$PPR = \frac{\text{Total Penjualan Perusahaan}}{\text{Total Penjualan Pesaing Utama}}$$

$$TPP = \frac{185.000.000}{160.000.000} \times 100\%$$

$$TPP = 1,16$$

A relative market share (RMS) value of 1.16 (>1) indicates that the sales of BG Company are higher than those of its main competitor. In the concept of the BCG Matrix, a relative market share value greater than 1 indicates that the company has a strong or dominant market position. This means that BG Company has a fairly strong competitive advantage in the food and beverage industry. A larger market share provides strategic advantages such as stronger bargaining power, better brand recognition, and higher potential profitability.

Position of BG Company in the BCG Matrix

Based on the calculation results:

- Market growth rate (MGR) = 54.17% (high)
- Relative market share (RMS) = 1.16 (>1)

Therefore, BG Company is positioned in the Star quadrant in the Boston Consulting Group (BCG) Matrix.

The Star quadrant represents companies that have a strong market share in industries with high growth. Companies in this position generally require significant investment to maintain growth, but they also have the potential to generate substantial profits in the long term.

THE FORMULATION OF A COMPETITIVE STRATEGY FOR A GROUP CAN USE THE BCG AND SWOT MATRICES

Gilbert Citra et al

This position indicates that BG Company is currently in an expansion phase and has good development prospects if managed with appropriate and sustainable strategies.

Strategy Based on the Star Position

Companies that are in the Star position are recommended to implement a growth strategy, which includes:

1. Maintaining and improving product and service quality.
2. Optimizing promotion and marketing activities to strengthen market position.
3. Expanding the market to increase sales volume.
4. Allocating resources and investments effectively to support long-term growth.

These strategies are expected to maintain market dominance while continuously improving the company's competitiveness.

Action Plan

An action plan is a set of activities that can be implemented to achieve the expected strategies and objectives. The action plan prepared in this study is based on the Star and Question Mark positions, according to the business conditions of BG Company and PT Tritunggal Adi Perkasa based on the results of the BCG Matrix analysis.

Table Action Plan Based on BCG Matrix Position

No	Business Unit	BCG Position	Strategy	Activities
1	Sushi Tei	Star (RMS > 1)	Backward integration	Strengthening cooperation with raw material suppliers to ensure product quality, operational cost efficiency, and long-term supply sustainability.
2	Pepper Lunch	Star (RMS > 1)	Forward integration	Optimizing distribution channels through the development of delivery services and the use of digital platforms to increase sales volume and expand market share.
3	Paradise Dynasty	Question Mark (RMS < 1)	Horizontal integration	Developing strategic partnerships with business partners and digital platforms to expand market networks and improve the company's competitiveness.
4	Marutama Ramen	Question Mark (RMS < 1)	Horizontal integration	Implementing market penetration strategies through intensive promotions and digital collaborations to increase market share and strengthen competitive position.

Source: Processed data (2025)

Table Action Plan for the Question Mark Position of BG Company

No	Strategy	Activities
1	Market penetration	Increasing promotions and attractive offer programs to attract consumer interest
2	Market development	Optimizing social media, using digital advertising, and collaborating with online platforms
3	Product development	Developing menu innovations according to consumer trends and preferences
4	Product evaluation	Conducting evaluations of menu items that are less popular

Source: Processed data (2025)

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